

OPEN!

Deliverable 2.1

Open Source Product Development Process Model

This work has been produced in the frame of the French-German interdisciplinary research project “Open! - Methods and tools for community-based product development”. The project received funding by the French and German national science agencies ANR (Agence Nationale de la Recherche, grant ANR-15-CE26-0012) and DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, grants JO 827/8-1 and STA 1112/13-1).

OPEN! - Methods and tools for community-based product development

Consortium:

#	Participant Legal Name	Short Name	Country
1	GRENOBLE ALPES UNIVERSITY, G-SCOP LABORATORY	G-SCOP	FR
2	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN, CHAIR OF INDUSTRIAL INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY	TUB-IIT	DE
3	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN, CHAIR OF QUALITY SCIENCE	TUB-QW	DE
4	CENTRE DE RECHERCHE EN GESTION DE GRENOBLE	CERAG	FR
5	ALEXANDER VON HUMBOLDT-INSTITUT FÜR INTERNET UND GESELLSCHAFT GMBH	HIIG	DE

Duration: 03/2016-09/2019

Contact (Principal Investigator): Prof Dr-Ing Roland JOCHEM

Address: Technische Universität Berlin, Sekretariat PTZ 3, Pascalstr. 8-9, 10587 Berlin

E-mail: roland.jochem@tu-berlin.de

Disclaimer: The contents of this document are not intended to replace consultation of any applicable legal sources or the necessary advice of a legal expert, where appropriate. All information in this document is provided "as is" and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user, therefore, uses the information at his/her sole risk and liability. For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no liability in respect of this document, which is merely representing the views of the author(s).

Review and approval status:

	Name and Surname	Role in the Project	Partner
Author(s)	Mies, Robert	Doctoral Researcher	TUB-QW
Reviewed by	Bonvoisin, Jérémy	Post-Doctoral Researcher	TUB-IIT
Approved by	Jochem, Roland	Principal Investigator	TUB-QW

History of changes:

Version	Date	Description of changes	By
0.8	19.07.2017	Initial draft	Robert Mies
0.9	27.07.2017	Manuscript for internal review	Robert Mies
1.0	21.08.2017	First version including revisions	Robert Mies

Keywords:

Open source hardware, open design, open source product development

2-1 - Open Source Product Development Process Model

This document is divided into two sections: The first section is aimed at delivering a **typology analysis** of complex, non-electronic open source hardware (OSH) projects to identify and characterise distinct project types. This will form the bases for the second section to visualise and discuss a **generic collaborative development process map with practitioners**.

At the beginning of each section the main motivation and objective are outlined. The chosen methodologies set the following agenda of tasks: (1.1) form a typology analysis approach, (1.2) clustering of project types, (1.3) discuss results of the typology analysis, (2.1) map a generic collaborative development process, (2.2) validate as well as adapt this process map based on semi-structured interviews with three originators of projects which managed to excel in collaborative development, and (2.3) discuss limitations and findings of the interview campaign.

1 Motivation and objective of the typology analysis

In order to describe any process, the research subject—the type of project—has to first be clearly defined. This leads to the objective to characterise projects within a typology analysis which is based on qualitative data acquired during the descriptive stage of the research project Open! (subtasks *1-2-1 - Making the Interviews and 1-3-1 Transcription Coding*). It is based on the assumption that heterogeneous types of projects exist which can be grouped according to process-related characteristics.

To date, no scholarly typology of different OSH projects exists. Previous work only relates to the field of open innovation as with the typology of Huizingh (2011)¹. He distinguishes between public innovation (open outputs and closed processes), private open innovation (open processes and closed outputs), and open innovation (open processes and outputs).

1.1 Typology analysis approach

The approach presented in this subsection is closely derived from recommendations of Welter (2006)² on typology analyses. These provided guidance in particular inasmuch as that two ways of clustering supplement each other: on the one side isolation of main characteristics of observed types, and on the other side identification of types through combination of characteristics. In this document these will be referred to as deductive approach and inductive approach.

First of all the inductive approach was followed, which was simply met by joint reflection within the research team on observed project archetypes.

The deductive approach required a more systematic and comprehensive set of activities. Welter (2006) distinguishes between two types of characteristics: constituting ones (reasons for existence of types) and descriptive ones (provide description of types). Identification and description of suitable evaluation criteria warranted the following activities: Brainstorming for collection of evaluation criteria, brief criteria and scales definition, and selection of most relevant process-based characteristics on a consensus basis.

The identified criteria were rated for 20 of the projects interviewed during qualitative data acquisition campaign (subtasks *1-2-1 Making the Interviews*). Coding analysis data of the interviews (subtask *1-3-1 Transcription Coding*) as well as interview summaries (subtasks *1-2-1 Making the Interviews*) served as information sources. Five iterations of individual ratings and criteria refinement were conducted to ensure sufficient shared understanding. In the first three rounds two research project members

¹ Huizingh, Eelko K. R. E. (2011). Open Innovation: State of the Art and Future Perspectives. *Technovation*, Open Innovation - ISPIIM Selected Papers, 31 (1): 2–9.

² Welter, M. (2006). Die Forschungsmethode der Typisierung. *WiSt-Wirtschaftswissenschaftliches Studium*, 35(2), 113-116.

participated, who were then joined by another two research project members for the last two rounds. Every time the results were compared by making deviations visible and discussing them in terms of different understandings of the project activities.

1.2 Clustering of project types

Observed project archetypes. During qualitative data acquisition campaign four project types stood out. Two of them presented pure forms at the opposite end of the spectrum of co-design vs. broadcasting. The other two represented different types of motivational patterns.

Co-design³ vs. broadcasting. Accounts from the first class of observed archetypes revealed substantial levels of collaborative development efforts. What was being described here, clearly were **community projects** engaging developers within dynamic OSH communities⁴ with significant growth potential. Distributed contributions (meaning from outside of the core team) played a significant role, while control on project strategy appeared to be surprisingly low. However, this presents the perpetual challenge of ensuring continuity and a high need for sharing documentation and coordination to enable accessibility to the design process for anyone who is interested.

Observations of another project archetype pointed in the complete opposite direction. Their operations were aimed at being **teamwork projects** forming very small, tight-knit design teams which generated all contributions internally and kept complete control. Their communities consisted largely of followers and replicators who may provide feedback and testing. However, the focus of sharing product documentation was strongly about broadcasting and diffusion of their designs for production, primarily by means of DIY.

Drive. Maher et al. (2011)⁵ define the conceptual space for collective design by the three dimensions of representations, communication and motivation. For the latter, they provide the following categories: Ideology, challenge, career, social, fun, reward, recognition, duty. It became obvious during the interviews that these motivations were not evenly distributed amongst projects.

Within the sample of interviewed projects, there were salient examples of what going by the terms above may be considered **ideological challenge projects**. They were strongly oriented towards collective problem solving for a larger cause (the meaning of ideology referred to here), thus demanding for a collective mindset. They were enthusiastic to meet complex and dynamic requirements with pragmatic and realistic solutions. This was accompanied with a great appreciation for distributed contributions, diffusion and with the drive of scaling up collective efforts.

Yet another class of geeky and arty projects was instead founded on an individualistic mindset. Relevant incentives here seemed to be fun and recognition, which is why these may be called **for-fun projects**. These projects were completely driven by their initiators' objectives and their specific skills or interests. Therefore, they tended to focus on hobbyist technology as well as lifestyle products for tinkering around. While a general interest for distributed development contributions existed in these projects, there was also no great desire to invest heavily into that.

Systematic criteria-based clustering. Three relevant criteria were identified, which are in line with the isolated characteristics of the observed archetypes. Iterative rating of projects and refinement of criteria led to the following list of criteria:

³ For definition of the term please see the following Open! glossary entry at URL: <https://opensourcedesign.cc/wiki/index.php/Co-design>.

⁴ For definition of the term please see the following Open! glossary entry at URL: <https://opensourcedesign.cc/wiki/index.php/Community>

⁵ Maher, M. L., Paulini, M., & Murty, P. (2011). Scaling up: From individual design to collaborative design to collective design. *Design Computing and Cognition DCC, 10*, 581-600.

Table 1: Rating criteria for typology analysis

Criterion	Pursued level of future collaborative development	Decentralisation of contributions	Drive
Description	The share of activities the core members are willing to involve the community in (volunteers not personally known by core-team)	The share of workload between core-team and volunteers	The overall orientation of the mission/vision statement or description as defined and pursued by the project founders or community
Rating = 1	comment	everything done by core-team	strong orientation towards purely for fun (geeky, hobbyist)
Rating = 2	provide feedback on the product (highlight design problems)	some tasks are made by people of the outside chosen by the core team	both, but orientation more towards for-fun
Rating = 3	suggest and implement concrete design propositions	design is done by the community (volunteers) but management is done by the core team	equally fun as well as problem-solving
Rating = 4	co-design (implement technical solutions in an interactive way)	design and management activities are done by the community	both, but orientation more towards real life problem-solving
Rating = 5	participation in management activities/strategy development		strong orientation towards real life problem-solving (to serve existing needs and disseminate project to a broad audience to reach this goal; from the initiators point of view)

Rating of the criteria for all 20 projects produced the typology depicted in Figure 1, which illustrates the gap between the pursued level of collaborative development (the target) and the actual decentralisation of contributions. Since discussion about assumptions on outliers following each rating cleared most of them, the intervals are based on the mean average of ratings as per Table 1.

As observed with *teamwork projects*, not all projects aim for co-design and are satisfied with a closed design process. The three projects at the lower bottom illustrate this. Huizingh (2011)⁶ refers to freely shared outcomes developed in private/closed settings as public innovations. Hence these projects can be considered as *public innovators*. From their approach they adhere to openness only in terms of output to aim for transparency and replicability.

Out of the 13 interviewed project which were assessed to have high ambitions for collaborative development, six managed to achieve intermediated or even high decentralisation of contributions and are thus adhering to accessibility of the design process. Thus, they are the only project type which follow the concept of OSPD⁷. These projects may therefore be considered as *collaborative innovators*. This derived type included the observed community projects as well as the ideological challenge projects, which provide a thorough characterisation. The common ground for this type is the clear intentions and extensive efforts put towards building up and aligning OSH communities around a collaborative process setup.

14 of the 20 interviewed projects were rated low in terms of decentralisation of contributions, which points towards a gap between target and actual. The most significant discrepancy can be found with the 7 projects on the lower right. They were expressing the intention to open their process for people to participate in development activities (accessibility), yet they have not managed to create the needed momentum for co-design. These projects may already provide accessibility to some extent but people are not making use of it. Therefore they may be considered as *involuntary isolated innovators*. There

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ For definition of the term please see the following Open! glossary entry at URL: https://opensource-design.cc/wiki/index.php/Open_Source_Product_Development.

may be various reasons for this situation to occur, such as a lack of available persons with methodological skills to create necessary momentum for collaborative development.

Additionally, the four empty fields suggest a major influence by the time variable as indicated by the light red arrow: People requirements and social dynamics of reciprocity during the growth of OSH communities make the establishing of steady collaboration efforts a time-consuming process. This could well raise substantial barriers which require a strong collective ambition. The fact that no project fell in that space could however also be due to the limited amount of interviewed projects.

The four remaining projects in between the categories of public innovators and the involuntary isolated innovators form a grey area, which mirrors the continuum of process openness and is somewhat expected.

Decentralisation of contributions	high [3 – 4]	none	none	4x projects collaborative innovators	↑ t?
	intermediate [2 – 3[none	none	2x projects	
	Low [1 – 2[public innovators 3x projects	4x projects	involuntary isolated innovators 7x projects	
		low [1 – 2[intermediate [2 – 3.5[high [3.5 - 5]	
		Pursued level of collaborative development			

Figure 1: Typology of three heterogeneous project types

Bonvoisin et al. (2017)⁸ highlight the major challenge of high people turnover within open source product development (OSPD) projects and the resulting need to ensure continuity. This makes motivating people to remain committed over time a major success factor. Figure 2 provides an insight on the relationship between decentralisation and drive, which is based on the observed types of for-fun projects and ideological challenge projects. It supports—as would be commonly expected—that ensuring continuity in the long run works better when communities are jointly following a larger cause than just doing things for fun. When the main objective is to create something for fun, there seems to be a lack of momentum for people to participate in collaborative development. At a certain stage of engagement people may simply require that their engagement in OSH projects follows a substantial purpose. Since doing things for fun seems to be of limited potential, unconstructive creation (waste, externalities) may automatically not be facilitated in the first place. Thus OSPD may be considered as an inherently sustainable concept.

⁸ [upcoming publication] Bonvoisin, J.; Thomas, L.; Mies, R.; Gros, C.; Stark, R.; Samuel, K.; Jochem, R.; Boujut, J.-F. (2017). Current state of practices in open source product development. *ICED17: The 21st International Conference on Engineering Design*. Submitted and accepted.

Figure 2: Relationship between decentralisation and drive

1.3 Limitations and results of typology analysis

Limitations. Summarizing as well as coding of semi-structured interviews with projects originators allowed a detailed understanding to rate the identified criteria. However, the used qualitative data is based on a relatively small cross-sectional sample of 20 projects. The sample was selected from a compiled list of 94 complex, non-electronic OSH projects according to propositions by members from the research team. Therefore the sample is not representative for the entire field of OSH. Since the OSH field has only been emerging in the last 10 years, it has to be recognised that the field may still evolve greatly.

Additionally, it cannot be guaranteed that the evaluation method was free of any confirmation bias. Although the research team was cautious to conduct data collection, coding, as well as subsequent interpretation efforts in an objective and scientific way, discussions on assumptions for diverging ratings may have led to distortions, e.g. overconfidence and harmonisation of ratings on insufficient data. Accordingly the categorisations are only estimates and should therefore only be published in anonymised form.

Results. The typology analysis identified three heterogeneous types of projects: Public innovators, involuntary isolated innovators and collaborative innovators. Inductive as well as deductively derived approaches matched well and allowed more detailed characterisation. Significant gaps between planned and actual levels of collaborative development were revealed. Community-based product development seems to be associated with facing real life challenges. Fun may be an important motivational aspect, but seems to be insufficient as a main driver to achieve collaborative development within OSH communities.

2 Motivation and objective of the collaborative development process map

To the knowledge of the author, OSPD processes have not been examined before on an activity level and generation of process variations are estimated within the frame of complex, non-electronic OSH products. Analyses of OSPD project setups as well as platform and tool development require a deeper understanding on present collaborative development processes in the field of OSH. The objective here is to map a generic process which reflects the reached understanding on relevant OSH project types and validate it through follow-up discussions with practitioners. This follows the assumption that a stable process setup has been reached.

However, it also presents the challenge that there cannot be a general process that covers all different development project settings in the field of OSH. From an industrial design point of view, collaborative innovators create a radically new environment of open collaboration engineering. Therefore this section seeks to model the collaborative development process of collaborative innovators on the activity level and validate it through semi-structured interviews with three originators of OSH community projects matching the category of collaborative innovators.

2.1 Design of generic collaborative development process map

The process to be mapped complements the workflow design of the version control repository and internet hosting service GitHub™ which was used as a template for the mapping of the collaborative development process with observations of previously interviewed OSH projects which had built up relatively stable OSH communities for co-development. The OSH field has been strongly influenced by this workflow, since it is an established standard for collaboration in (open source) software development projects—the roots of the OSH phenomenon. Observations within the research project Open! revealed a use of GitHub by about one third of complex, non-electronic OSH projects. They were using GitHub's platform offerings for software, electric, as well as mechanical hardware portions of the development scope. Although it only provides a makeshift solution for the latter two, the workflow itself provides a number of basic elements (i.e. issue lists, versioning, merge and deploy) that will have to be incorporated in future OSPD development platforms (see 3-4).

In the following part of this subsection the mapped process design will be illustrated:

Starting points. The generic map of the collaborative development process is triggered by four starting points as below in Figure 3. Three of them require the generation of a tasks in a modular issue list on a central, public system. This task consists of basic information such as a description, requirements and authorship. The creation of a public task serves as an open call inviting anyone to claim and perform it. Tasks enclosed by the dotted line are claimed by the community. To enhance the relative share of distributed contributions is the main lever for OSPD projects as it equates to effectivity and progress.

Claiming of tasks from an issue list can first of all occur pro-actively through *self-selection* by community members. Another way is for someone to be requested directly because of their skills, experience or availability, which is referred to as *task assignment*. This person may then agree to take on the task or not. Tasks may also be performed centrally by the core team, although this should not be the first-best solution as process guidance and steering activities need to be covered by them. Therefore it is idealised that tasks are first of all created publicly and only escalated to the core team as a last resort.

However, logging of tasks in modular issue lists is not always the case. A share of contributions is always made without having been defined publicly beforehand, which is referred here as *proactive task initiation*. Here someone has an idea and decides to work on it him/herself.

Figure 3: Starting points of collaborative process

Collaborative process map. From there the designed collaborative process map is built up in accordance with the industry standard *Business Process Model and Notation 2.0* (BPMN) as released by the Object Management Group, Inc. (OMG). It is depicted in Figure 4. The process design defines two swim lanes of the development community as well as the core team which takes care of the coordination and convergence of distributed development activities.

The use of GitHub's workflow design is first of all reflected by the following action-items:

- forking* - make local copies of working documentation,
- to make a commit* - save new versions of local copies,
- pull request* - submit commits to the main project or a sub-branch,
- merge and deploy* - integrate contributions with the main project.

For any contributions to be created, the actions of forking, making a commit, and pull request have to occur at least once in the listed order. If the contribution is accepted it can be merged. This leads to a closing of the task and an update in the project repository. Merging may occur manually (asynchronous) or tool-supported (in synchronous, concurrent workflows, e.g. in OnShape).

Tasks which are performed centrally by the core team (see *central task fulfilment*) are illustrated as an ad-hoc process (marked by the tilde symbol at the bottom of the task), whereby either a core team member decides to fulfil it him/herself, or get external support (i.e. from professional developers, developers of other community, etc.).

Distributed contributions follow a sub-process referred to herein as *guided contribution*. Following forking, editing and local commit(s), a pull request of the new version is made (all by a development community member) to seek for review of the contribution. The core-team is then informed that a file has been submitted to be reviewed for acceptance. Performed reviews are then publicly stored for traceability. The review either concludes acceptance of the contribution or generates critical feedback to provide suggestions for improvement. Those improvements are then followed-up by the developer which leads to another iteration. At any point, tasks may however be abandoned, e.g. because they turn out too complex or developers become inactive.

Figure 4: Collaborative process map

2.2 Validation and adaptation of generic collaborative process map

The collaborative process map as depicted in Figure 4 was presented and outlined to three project initiators of projects matching the category of collaborative innovators. Afterwards they were asked in a semi-structured interview to compare and contrast it with their projects. The aim of the interviews was to validate the collaborative process map and learn more about functions of the different mechanisms. For preparation relevant questions related to the different process steps were developed beforehand. The questions were only asked where appropriate. This subsection presents main results of the interviews and closes with an adapted process map considering some objections from the interviews.

In the following part of this subsection the findings of the three interviews are summarised:

Team composition and collaboration leverage. To begin with the distinction of a core team and a development community was not rejected by the interviewees, which was not a given. A shared understanding on this point was necessary for subsequent questions. In one of the projects formal roles are assigned based on a hierarchal training scheme which has to be passed in order of ranks. Here two core team members act as supervisors and mentors within two established development teams. In this project the total share of distributed contributions was estimated at about 75%. In the other two projects the boundaries were described to be more fluid and based on meritocracy and commitment. One has a relatively stable core team consisting of three to four members. Here the total share of distributed contributions was estimated at about on third. The composition of the other project's core team is highly dynamic and based on attendance of regular core team meetings. The share of distributed contributions in this project ranged from 50% for hardware issues, to 70% for issues connected to practitioner's expertise on subject matter within the respective product environment, and to 80% for software issues.

Task creation. In all three cases set tasks are technical, organisational (within the meaning of coordination) as well as administrative, which are all treated in the same way. In theory they could be created by anyone, yet in two of the projects it is the responsibility of the core team. One of them even

uses a project list with predefined activity items which covers an entire product development cycle. Proactive task creation is also part and parcel of collaborative work in all three projects: In one of the three projects it is even the most common way of how tasks are created. While one interviewee noted that people like to work on ideas they have come up with themselves, another expressed that in their project it is seen as an important success factor. Yet the third interviewee stressed that—in contrast with the process map—in their project proactively initiated tasks are usually put on public issue lists by their initiators before they start working on them. He/she explained that this is common-place within their project as awareness to document is widespread.

Task assignment. Self-selection and individual assignment are consistently described as complements by the three interviewees. People tend to generally claim tasks they are comfortable with. At the same time persons with corresponding skills are often requested to take on specific tasks, the moment they are created. Nevertheless, double work does not appear to be an issue: Division of responsibility works surprisingly well, because developers typically communicate what they are working on and a sufficient level of alignment seems to be in place (see below ‘Process overview’). Interestingly, one interviewee noted how in their project people are even encouraged to develop different solutions for the same problem.

Review and feedback on pull requests. Committees (online as well as offline) and special roles for review and feedback activities are installed in all three projects. Within two of the projects anyone willing to contribute in this way simply steps forward. At one of them, reviews are often informal or not even required to accept contributions. At the other one, reviews are also done within the development community as they often have skills the core team does not possess. In the third project reviews are done by the core team and pre-structured template forms are used for feedback.

Merge and deploy. In all three cases the core team remains to make the final selection of viable contributions for inclusion in the official version. One interviewee noted that—in contrast with the process map—tasks do not get closed, because they can always be picked up again in the future; it is only the priority that changes.

Process overview. Regular team meetings and consultations were mentioned as important means to keep track. Issue management systems allow developers to own tasks, which according to the interviewees is commonly made use of. Also developers are encouraged to keep track of ongoing activities, e.g. through following wiki changes. At one of the projects developers even have individual work logs which are linked together. This project also uses a list of predefined development activity items to track the overall progress through a completion rate.

Overall process validity. At the end of the interviews, the matching of the flows with the respective settings as well as the overall applicability of the generic process map was confirmed by all three interviewees apart from the mentioned minor objections.

Sharing of responsibilities between the core team and the development community. While the distinction between core team and development community was accepted by the interviewees to describe the team composition (see above at ‘Team composition and collaboration leverage’), the same was indirectly put in question on the activity level: From the above *task creation*, *individual task assignment*, as well as *review and feedback* were not exclusively conducted by the core team, and therefore make up another form of distributed contributions.

Adapted collaborative process map. The interviews prompted changes of the collaborative process map, which are adopted in Figure 5. The continuous nature of tasks was considered for the task of *merge and deploy* by it triggering a “change of task priority in public issue list” instead of “close task in public issue list”. For the task *proactive task initiation* the triggering of a “new entry in public issue list” was added to reflect the apparent documentation awareness. Furthermore, the inserted dotted line reflects how the boundaries of the swim lanes may or not cover the sharing of responsibilities on *task creation*, *individual task assignment*, as well as *review and feedback*.

Figure 5: Revised collaborative process map

2.3 Discussion of collaborative development process map

Discussion. An interesting ambiguity was also presented on the distinction of the core team and the development community: While this served to be useful for role description, it did not with regard to division of responsibilities. Since knowledge is widely dispersed, *task creation*, *individual task assignment*, as well as *review and feedback* may not just be attributed to the core team but as well as to the development community. These contributions may then from *distributed second order contributions*, as compared to the *distributed first order contributions* through the actions of forking, making a commit, and pull request. Unlike in traditional business process environments, clear division of responsibility could be too limiting for particular circumstances.

Also it should be noted, that treating parallel efforts to solve the same problem as an opportunity means giving precedence to seeking the most effective solution over aiming for maximised efficiency. This is a very essential distinction which characterises the OSH environment.

In addition, connecting back to theory the subtle fact that tasks are never completed leads to a greater understanding of the collaborative development process presented herein. It shows on the activity level how *an on-going process of continuous improvement* is entered as highlighted by Bonvoisin & Boujut (2015)⁹.

Limitations. GitHub itself is used within two of the three projects, so there may be a direct influence on workflow design. In addition the three sampled projects may not be representative for the whole category of collaborative innovators. Yet, all three interviewees confirmed applicability of the generic collaborative development process map independent from each other.

Furthermore, what really differentiates projects, is the controls logic (i.e. rules for when which alternative path is followed), which is not detailed in the process map. As the process map allows for

⁹ Bonvoisin, J., Boujut, J.F. (2015). Open design platforms for open source product development: current state and requirements. *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Engineering Design (ICED 15)*, Vol 8: *Innovation and Creativity*, Milan, Italy, 27-30.07.15, pp. 11-22.

more structured as well as flexible approaches, it supports the identification of different approaches by serving as a template. Indeed the interviews did not only help to validate the collaborative process map, but also to reach a better understanding of how the different mechanisms and their functions are applied in practice.

The investigated projects were described to have a maximum leverage of central to distributed contribution of 1:3, when theoretically, the share of distributed contributions should be scalable to unlimited levels. Thus the extent to which this process really democratises product design is to be further explored. OSH is still a relatively young phenomenon which has only emerged within the last decade and not many projects have managed to build stable development communities.

Conclusion. Through the three semi-structure interviews with initiators of projects matching the category of collaborative innovators, the actual application of the generic collaborative development process within practice could be confirmed within some deviations which were included in a revised process design. Upon inquiry on the various mechanisms, each of them turned out to fulfil vital function. Moreover, the usage of issue management systems, structured feedback mechanisms, as well as creating process awareness can be viewed as best practice examples within the field of OSH.

Conclusions can be drawn from this research on the process versioning logic as it is applied in practice. The three interviews presented different mechanisms which provide building blocks allowing structured and customized design of collaborative development processes, which may be more flexible or structured. The designed process map can serve as a basis to conduct empirical research on specific success factors as well as implications on effectiveness.